

CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF THE POSSIBILITIES AND LIMITATIONS OF THE MICROMECHANICAL TEST TECHNIQUES

Muriel Desaeger and Ignaas Verpoest

Katholieke Universiteit Leuven
Departement Metaalkunde en Toegepaste Materiaalkunde
de Croylaan 2, 3001 Leuven (Belgium)

Abstract

Several micromechanical test techniques are currently used for the characterisation of the fibre/matrix interface properties. Although they are powerful, they suffer from some limitations. The aim of this paper is to give the state of the art concerning these test techniques. The data reduction schemes used to derive the interface properties from the experimental test results are discussed as well as the experimental parameters which have an important influence on the experimental test results. The scatter on the results obtained with the three techniques is quantified and discussed.

Keywords: Micromechanics, fibre-matrix interface, microindentation, pull-out, fragmentation.

1. Introduction

The bond between the fibre and the matrix is of tremendous importance in composite materials. Almost all the mechanical properties of these materials are influenced by the quality of the interface and improvement of 200% of the interlaminar shear strength has already been obtained by choosing adapted interface conditions (1).

The interface properties have therefore to be controlled. Micromechanical test techniques are the most appropriate techniques for their characterisation. In these micromechanical, i.e. single fibre tests, the interface is directly loaded and subjected to failure. they are the pull-out, the fragmentation and the microindentation tests. In the beginning of their existence, the micromechanical test techniques have been developed in order to outline the benefits introduced by the use of various fibre surface treatments. When two systems were compared, the aim was to know for which of them the adhesion between the fibre and the matrix was stronger. Now that the tests are well-established, more attention has to be paid to the domain of application of the tests and to the validity of the derived absolute value of the interfacial shear strength properties as obtained from the three techniques. This work is presented in this paper.

2. Domain of application of each micromechanical test

Concerning the domain of application of the tests, it is clear that only in a few fibre-matrix systems all three techniques can be used for the characterisation of the interface properties. Very often, only one test technique is appropriate for the system considered (Table.1). This explains why no single technique may be considered as "the best" one. They have to be seen as complementary techniques (2).

	Fragmentation	Pull-out	Microindentation
Fibres			
Carbon	OK if Df not too small	idem	Risc of fibre splitting
Glass	OK if max strain matrix large enough	OK	Risc of fibre rupture
Polymer fibres	OK if clean fibre rupture	OK	Not possible
Matrices			
Thermosets	OK if max strain matrix > 3* max strain fibre	OK	OK
Thermoplastics	Difficult specimen preparation	idem	OK if polishing is OK
Metals	(No evidence)	OK for thick fibres	OK
Ceramics	(Some inverse fragmentation)	(No evidence)	OK
Interface			
	OK	Difficult for high τ_i	Difficult for low τ_i

Table 1: Domain of application of each micromechanical test techniques

More in detail, it can be said that most of the time the carbon fibres can be tested with the fragmentation, the pull-out and the microindentation tests providing that the diameter of the fibre is not too small. Small diameter induces large problems for the preparation of the test specimens. Carbon fibres with a high degree of anisotropy can also not be tested with the microindentation test due to the problem of fibre splitting.

Glass fibres can be tested with the fragmentation test. Nevertheless, due to the large strain to failure of these fibres, the test is rapidly limited by the strain to failure of the matrix. Pull-out and microindentation can be used for the characterisation of the glass fibre interface providing that the quality of interface between the fibre and the matrix is not too high, so that matrix yielding and rupture can be avoided.

For polymer fibres like aramid or PE-fibres, the pull-out test is the best because it allows to avoid fibre splitting induced by the anisotropy of the fibre structure, as occurs in the microindentation and fragmentation test.

Concerning the matrices, most thermosets can be used in the three tests. In the case of the fragmentation test, however the strain to failure of the matrix has to be large enough to ensure sufficient documentation of the process.

Thermoplastic matrices can be studied with the micromechanical tests if the difficulties in preparing the specimens can be solved. These problems concern the specimen manufacturing procedure for the fragmentation and the pull-out tests and the polishing of the specimens for the microindentation test. If the adhesion is too low, the interface can indeed be destroyed during the polishing step.

3. Validity of the interfacial properties derived from the three tests.

The potential and limitations of each test are not only determined by the kind of material, but also by the following factors:

- the *stress state at the interface* and more precisely at the place of failure,
- the *failure criteria* used for the calculation of the interface properties out of the experimental data,
- the *experimental parameters* by which the failure is influenced.

These three points can be discussed separately for each test. Their discussion allows to outline to which extend the current assumptions made, introduce inaccuracy in the derived interface properties. Moreover, based on the results of a Round Robin test programme initiated by

Pitkethly and Favre (7) the validity of the results (quantified with the aid of their coefficient of variation) obtained with the three techniques has been calculated.

3.1 The microindentation test

A general scheme of the microindentation test is presented in figure 1. The microindentation test is currently carried out to characterise the interface properties in polymer or ceramic matrix composites.

Fig. 1: Configuration of the microindentation test

The *stress state* assumed in this test depends on the material of interest.

In the case of ceramic fibre composite no real bond (chemical or physico-chemical) is assumed between the fibre and the matrix and the stress transfer between the fibre and the matrix is directly and only related to the frictional shear stress transfer. The frictional shear stress has two components: the first one is related to the residual thermal stresses and the second one to the Poisson effect. The compressed fibre slides through the currently relatively thin specimen used. The interfacial shear stress is mostly assumed to be constant along the fibre length(3).

In the case of polymer matrix specimens, the bond (chemical or physico-chemical) between the fibre and matrix is quite strong. This induces that the applied force on the fibre first has to reach a critical value so that the bond between the fibre and the matrix is ruptured. Only then, the fibre can slide into or through the specimen. In this case, attention is focussed on the evaluation of the stress state existing before the start of any sliding. The shear-lag model (elastic model) is often therefore used and the profile of a shear stress state showing a maximum interfacial shear stress at the specimen surface is obtained (2).

For both polymeric and ceramic materials, most of the analytical models used up to now, are simple one dimensional models and consider only the presence of the shear stress at the interface. Only few more advanced models pay attention to the other stresses like the radial interfacial stress or tangential stress (8).

The *failure criteria* used to derive interfacial properties are, in all cases, maximum shear stress criteria. In the case of the ceramic matrix composite, it allows the determination of the interfacial frictional resistance (τ_{fri}) and in the case of the polymer matrix composites, the interfacial bond shear strength (τ_{deb}).

The fact that simple failure criteria are used limited of course the validity of the derived shear strength properties. Mandell (8) and Marotzke(9) have shown that the radial stresses may be also a determining factor for the initiation of failure. In the case of a carbon-epoxy system the radial stresses at the interface are in compression, and in the case of a carbon-borosilicate glass matrix system the radial stresses at the interface are in tension. The presence of these stresses and the fact that they are not taken into account in the failure criteria will induce over- or underestimation of the real interfacial shear strength. Moreover, the exact the shear strength can be determined only when the exact location of the crack is known. Compressive radial stresses at the interface change into tension radial stresses in the matrix at a certain distance from the interface. Depending on the relative strength (shear, radial, ...) of the interface and of the matrix, the crack will occur in one or in the other material. This shows that a more adapted

failure criterion would be a quadratic failure criterion applied to each place at the interface and in the matrix.

Experimental parameters can also influence the validity of the derived interfacial properties from the microindentation test. The results of a multiclient study performed on ten different types of composite materials have shown that the most critical experimental parameters are: the polishing procedure for the preparation of the specimens, the kind of indenter tip used for the application of the load, the determination of the load inducing the debonding of the fibre and the fibre environment.

In order to quantify the effects related to the specimen preparation procedure and these related to the test procedure, results of a Round Robin test programme (7) have been evaluated. Twelve laboratories, amongst which the laboratory of the authors, participated in this program. Each laboratory was supplied with the same Courtaulds XA fibre in untreated and treated conditions and with a quantity of epoxy resin, hardener and catalyst, all from the same batch. Some laboratories were supplied with composite plates made of the same materials. A common cure cycle was chosen for sample preparation. Each laboratory conducted the tests according to their own experimental and data reduction procedures.

The microindentation tests were performed in four labs. Our lab was one of them. Two of the labs used the same test equipment, which is now commercialised. Another lab used a self-built equipment while in our lab the Nanoindenter was used. The main differences in the test procedures followed in each lab have to do with the specimen preparation, the shape of the indenter, and the method to monitor the load at debonding. Two labs experienced fibre splitting during the tests and one of them found it impossible to extract sufficient data to calculate an interfacial bond shear strength.

The mean coefficient of variation (CV %) on the raw data and on the interface properties found in each lab separately or by taking the results of all the labs into account are presented in Table.2.

CV %	Raw data Each lab	Raw data All labs	Interfacial strength Each lab	Interfacial strength All lab
Microindentation	10%	20%	15%	10%
Fragmentation	11%	22%	17%	30%
Pull-out	12%	30%	12%	26%
Mean value	10-12%	20-30%	10-20%	10-30%

Table 2: Summary of the coefficient of variation on the raw data and on the interfacial properties derived from the three tests; by considering each lab separately or all together.

In summary, for the microindentation test, it can be said that:

- when one specific test procedure is followed to report on the microindentation test results, the CV % on these results is about 10% for the raw data and 15% for the interfacial bond shear strength;
- when results obtained by following various test procedures are considered, the CV % on the final results on bond shear strength is about 10% (by taking only three labs into account).

Finally, it can be concluded that the most important advantage of the microindentation test lies in the fact that real composite parts can be tested. Therefore, the results obtained with this kind of specimen are in close correlation with what is occurring in a real composites. On the other hand, the test has some disadvantages too. The validity of the obtained results is indeed greatly

influenced by the test procedure and by the data reduction scheme used for the determination of the interface properties. The absolute value of the interface properties can also not be straightforward evaluated as such due to the complexity of the stress field around the loaded fibre.

3.2 The fragmentation test

The fragmentation test involves a single fibre embedded into a dog bone specimen of matrix (Fig. 2). This specimen is subjected to a monotonically increasing tensile strain in the direction of the fibre axis. Since the fibre failure strain is lower than that of the matrix, the fibre starts to fracture into small segments within the matrix. Continued application of strain to the specimen results in repetition of this fragmentation process until the remaining fibre lengths become so short that the shear stress transfer along their length can no longer build up enough tensile stresses in the fibre to cause any further failure. During the fragmentation process, various kinds of cracks, initiated from the fibre rupture, can propagate simultaneously with the rupture of the fibre. These cracks involve either the interface or the matrix material.

Fig. 2: The fragmentation process

Many authors have studied the *stress transfer* occurring between a short fibre and a matrix during the loading condition characteristic of the fragmentation test. The first, and most famous ones, were Cox (10) and Kelly (11). These famous models were later further developed by the authors into the so-called "partially elastic" model (4).

The Cox model also known as the elastic model or the shear-lag model, is based on the fact that both the fibre and the matrix are considered to be elastic. Some assumptions are made concerning the stresses in the matrix surrounding the fibre. This model is a one dimensional model allowing the determination of the tensile stress profile in the fibre and the profile of the shear stress at the interface. The tensile stress is equal to zero at the fibre ends and the shear stress is zero in the middle of the fibre.

The Kelly model, known as the plastic model, assumes plastic yielding of the matrix surrounding the fibre end. When plastic flow occurs at the interface, the interface shear stresses are considered to be equal to the yield stress in shear of the matrix, which is assumed to be constant. In the middle of the fibre, where the matrix has not yet yielded, the shear stresses are assumed to be equal to zero.

The "partially elastic" model is more complete. This model considers elastic stress transfer between the fibre and the matrix at the place where the link between the fibre and the matrix is

not yet broken or where the matrix has not yet yielded (i.e. the shear stress is assumed not equal to zero but similar to the value proposed in the Cox model). A non-elastic stress transfer near the fibre ends where fibre-matrix debonding or matrix yielding has taken place. Other models, three dimensional analytical models (12) or FEM models (13) have also been developed but they are not yet currently used.

The *failure criteria* applied to these models to derive the interface properties from the experimental data are most of the time a maximum shear stress criteria. In some cases the criteria are however based on energetic considerations (14). Nevertheless, it is important to make the difference between the maximum mean shear stress criteria which is currently applied to the Cox and the Kelly models and the more complex shear stress criteria applied to the "partially-elastic" model. In this last model, the two interfacial shear properties: the interfacial bond shear strength as well as the interfacial frictional resistance, are taken into account in place of a mean shear strength. This makes the power of this model; by using this more realistic model and by considering separately the bond shear strength and the frictional resistance of the interface, the recording of the profile of the fibre fragment length as well as this of the debonding ratio as a function of the applied strain, allows the separate determination of the two interfacial properties.

Nevertheless, even if the "partially elastic" model has quite a number of advantages to compare to the more simple models, the "partially elastic" model has also some limitations. The radial stresses are considered only in the debonding zone as far as they create frictional stress transfer and not in the not debonded zone. The model is still a one dimensional model and, the failure criteria considered only shear stresses. Furthermore, the model contains a certain factor R indicating the distance in the matrix where the matrix is not any more influenced by the fibre rupture. This distance is extremely difficult to evaluate experimentally and theoretically.

The test results are also influenced by some *experimental parameters*. The tension applied to the fibre, the kind of molding technique used, the curing condition which influenced the thermal stresses at the fibre-matrix interface, the evaluation of the fibre debonding length are some of these parameters.

Based on the Round Robin test programme previously mentioned, the scatter on the results introduced by the effect of the experimental parameters has been quantified (Table 2).

The scatter (expressed in coefficient of variation) on the fragmentation test raw data is in the order of 10%. The scatter increases to almost 20% when the raw data obtained in different labs are taken together. This increase of 10% is directly related to the experimental parameters and differences in test procedures. Finally, it can also be said that the coefficient of variation calculated on all the reported interfacial shear strength data is equal to 30%. This large scatter is mainly due to the scatter in the experimental data, in the evaluation of the fibre strength and in the kind of model used for the evaluation of the interface properties.

3.3 The pull-out test

Fig. 3 Configuration of a pull-out test.

The pull-out experiment, which is believed to possess some of the characteristics of the fibre pull-out process occurring in real composite parts, consists of the loading of a fibre embedded perpendicularly to the surface of the matrix block or thin film (Fig. 3). A steadily increasing force is applied to the free end of the fibre in order to pull it out of the matrix. During the pull-out test, the load and the displacement applied to the fibre are monitored until either pull-out occurs or the fibre fractures because its embedded length is too large.

The *stress state* at the fibre-matrix interface is often assessed in a pull-out test by the use of a linear elastic model: the Greszczuk's model (5) which is sometimes further developed into a model taking simultaneously bonding and non-constant frictional effects into account (6). In the Greszczuk model the mean shear stress is expressed as a function of the fibre embedded length. Extrapolation of the mean shear stress to a fibre embedded length equal to zero allows the determination of the interfacial bond shear strength. In the case of the more developed model of Hsueh (6), the partial debond stress (i.e. the applied stress needed to debond the fibre and to pull it out of the matrix) is expressed as a function of the interfacial bond shear strength, the frictional resistance and the fibre embedded length.

Again in both cases, the applied *failure criteria* is a maximum shear stress criteria or a criterion where the bond shear strength and frictional shear resistance is taken into account. Until now, no complex stress criteria taking into account the radial stresses have been proposed. These radial stresses are however very important. On one hand, due to the thermal stresses induced by the curing conditions, the interface is radially in compression. This means also that the matrix around the interface is then in tension. The application of the load induces on the other hand radial tensile stresses at interface. All these effects (added to the effect of load introduction and thermal effects on all the other stresses) have to be combined to come up with a more exact understanding of the failure initiation and propagation at the interface or in the matrix around the interface.

In this test also *experimental parameters* can influence the final results.

These are: the way by which the load is introduced in the specimen, the amount of resin used, the measurement of the fibre embedded length, the fibre alignment during the application of the load, the stiffness of the equipment used, the free fibre length.

The spread on the pull-out results has been quantified (Table 2). The CV % on the raw data obtained in each lab is about 12%, This CV % increases to 25% when the interfacial properties obtained in the different lab are considered all together.

4. Conclusion

After having presented the state of the art concerning the three micromechanical test techniques, it really appears that the three techniques are complementary. Some systems can only be tested with one technique whereas others need the use of another test. All of them need however the development of more powerful data reduction schemes if they want to be used for the exact determination of interfacial properties. To compare different fibre-matrix systems, the existing data reduction schemes are sufficient, but when absolute values have to be found out of the experimental results, complex data reduction schemes where a three dimensional stress state, and complex failure criteria are considered, would have to be used. In a first step the accuracy on the derived results could greatly be improved by the development and implementation of test standards. The use of standards would probably allow the reduction of the CV % on results obtained in different labs to a value of 10% instead of the actual 20%.

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